

Effect of ethylenediaminetetra acetic acid, 2,2'-bipyridyl and manganese(II) on the reduction of chromium(VI) by D-glucose in presence of HClO₄

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Abstract : Kinetic data for the chromium(VI)-D-glucose redox system in presence of complexing agents are reported for the first time. The reaction is first-order each in [Cr^{VI}] and [D-glucose]. The kinetics reveal complex order dependence with [HClO₄]. The zero-order kinetics with respect to [HClO₄] at low concentrations shifts to higher order at higher concentration. Ethylenediaminetetra acetic acid (EDTA) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (bpy) catalyze the reaction whereas Mn^{II} has no effect. In the EDTA- and bpy-catalyzed paths, Cr^{VI}-EDTA and Cr^{VI}-bpy complexes have respectively been suggested as the active oxidant species. On the basis of various experimental data and the product characterization, the most plausible mechanisms have been proposed for the reactions.

Keywords : Manganese(II), 2,2'-bipyridyl, chromium(VI), D-glucose, EDTA, HClO₄.

Introduction

Oxidation of carbohydrates by transition metal ions (V^V, Cr^{VI}, Th^{III}, Mn^{VII}, Ce^{IV} and colloidal MnO₂) are of special importance due to their biological relevance¹⁻⁵. The redox chemistry of Cr^{VI} with biologically relevant molecules is also important in the intracellular metabolism of Cr^{VI}^{6,7}. In the case where Cr^{VI} serves as an oxidizing agent, the possible intermediate species are Cr^V and Cr^{IV}. The existence of different Cr^{VI} species in acid solutions and the tendency of Cr^{III} (reaction product) to form a variety of complexes, give the systems of considerable complexity⁸. Therefore, Cr^{VI} oxidations provide kinetics with challenging mechanistic possibilities due to the ability of chromium to exist in different oxidation states⁹.

It has been established that complexing agents (EDTA, bpy, oxalic acid, picolinic acid, α -hydroxy acids and Mn^{II}) have some effect in the oxidation of different organic reductants by Cr^{VI}¹⁰⁻¹³. The Mn^{II} species show unique behaviour (catalyst, inhibitor or no effect) in many Cr^{VI} redox reactions^{12,13}. Picolinic acid, EDTA and bpy neither self oxidize nor act as true catalysts, but are lost during the course of the reaction. Mitewa and Bontchev pointed out that the mechanism is unclear in the presence

of complexing agents⁹. The kinetics of Cr^{VI} oxidation of several monosaccharides are well documented in literature but the studies of the oxidation in presence of complexing agents, until recently, been lacking. The kinetics of Cr^{VI} oxidation of D-glucose in presence of EDTA, bpy and Mn^{II} may reveal novel features and, therefore, the present study was undertaken to gain further insight into the mechanism. Incidentally, this study appears to be the first of its kind.

Results and discussion

Product analysis : To confirm the nature of the reduction product of Cr^{VI}, the reactants (D-glucose, Cr^{VI}, HClO₄ and EDTA) were mixed at 313 K. Although visual observation indicated that the reaction was completed in 30 min, the oxidized reaction mixture was kept for ca. 20 min and then UV-Vis spectra were recorded (Fig. 1). The most characteristic part of the Cr^{III} spectrum is the two d-d transitions observable in the 350-650 nm region³. The spectra of the compound under study consists of two bands with $\lambda_{\max} = 410$ and 575 nm whereas in presence of EDTA two peaks are also observable with $\lambda_{\max} = 400$ and 550 nm (Fig. 1). It is well known that EDTA forms a complex with Cr^{III}¹⁴, due to which λ_{\max} of aqua Cr^{III} shifts to shorter wavelength. Present λ_{\max}

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of reaction mixtures after completion of the reaction containing $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $[\text{D-glucose}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.46 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ and $[\text{EDTA}] = 1.0$ (■), 3.0 (●) and $4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ (▲).

values are in good agreement with the literature values¹⁴. In the absence of EDTA, the end product was the Cr^{III} aqua ion.

The oxidation product of D-glucose was characterized as follows : an oxidized reaction mixture was treated with alkaline hydroxylamine solution. The presence of lactone was tested by the ferric chloride-hydrochloric acid blue test¹⁵. Under the kinetic conditions, qualitative identification of product was carried out by paper chromatography³. The lactone was identified against an authentic sample (1,4-D-glucolactone) using 4 : 1 : 5 *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water eluant. A three-stage dip of AgNO_3 , NaOH and $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ was used to visualize the paper chromatograms.

The rate law :

The effect of $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ on the reaction rate was studied at constant $[\text{D-glucose}] (= 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1})$, $[\text{HClO}_4] (= 1.6 \text{ mol L}^{-1})$ and temperature ($= 313 \text{ K}$). The values of rate constants (k_{obs}) are summarized in Table 1. The independence of k_{obs} over a range of $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ is in agreement with a first-order dependence on $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_{\text{T}}$ and the reaction follows a pseudo first-order rate law, i.e.

$$v = \frac{-d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_{\text{T}} \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Effects of $[\text{D-glucose}]$, $[\text{HClO}_4]$ and $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ on the oxidation of D-glucose by Cr^{VI} in HClO_4 at 313 K

$10^3 [\text{D-Glucose}]$ (mol L^{-1})	$[\text{HClO}_4]$ (mol L^{-1})	$10^4 [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ (mol L^{-1})	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1})
1.0	2.0	1.0	1.2 (1.4) ^a
2.0			1.6 (1.9)
3.0			2.6 (3.9)
4.0			3.8 (4.7)
5.0			4.2 (5.2)
6.0			5.4 (5.9)
2.0	0.46	1.0	0.49
	1.16		0.50
	1.62		0.52
	2.00		1.5
	2.32		2.6
	3.01		5.6
	3.48		9.9
2.0	2.0	1.0	1.6
		2.0	1.5
		3.0	1.6
		4.0	1.5
		5.0	1.6

^aIn presence of EDTA ($= 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and HClO_4 ($= 1.62 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$).

Order in $[\text{HClO}_4]$: A series of kinetic runs were performed within $[\text{HClO}_4]$ range of 0.16 to 3.48 mol L^{-1} at constant $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] (= 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1})$, $[\text{D-glucose}] (= 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1})$ and temperature ($= 313 \text{ K}$). The pseudo first-order rate constants are given in Table 1. The effect of $[\text{HClO}_4]$ variation indicates that zero-order dependence at low $[\text{HClO}_4]$ shifts to higher order at higher concentrations. The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\log \text{HClO}_4$ resulted in two straight line portions with slopes ($= 0.0$ and 1.2), further confirming the order with respect to $[\text{HClO}_4]$ to be zero and more than one at lower and higher $[\text{HClO}_4]$, respectively.

Order in D-glucose : At constant $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] (= 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1})$, $[\text{HClO}_4] (= 1.62 \text{ mol L}^{-1})$ and temperature ($= 313 \text{ K}$), the reaction rate increased with an increase in $[\text{D-glucose}] (= 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ to } 6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1})$. The k_{obs} values are summarized in Table 1. The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\log [\text{D-glucose}]$ was linear with slope ($= 1.0$), indicating first-order dependence on $[\text{D-glucose}]$.

Table 2. Effects of complexing agents on the oxidation of D-glucose ($= 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol L⁻¹) by Cr^{VI} ($= 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol L⁻¹) in HClO₄ ($= 1.62$ mol L⁻¹) at 313 K

Complexing agents ^a					
10 ⁴ [EDTA] (mol L ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ [bpy] (mol L ⁻¹)	10 ³ [Mn ^{II}] (mol. L ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ k _{obs1} (s ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ k _{obs2} (s ⁻¹)	10 ⁴ k _{obs3} (s ⁻¹)
0.0	0.0	0.0	0.56	0.56	0.56
0.2	0.2	1.0	0.76	0.62 (1.9) ^b	0.55
0.6	0.6	2.0	1.2	0.75 (2.2)	0.56
1.0	1.0	3.0	1.5	1.2 (2.6)	0.54
1.4	1.5	4.0	1.6	1.3 (2.8)	0.55
2.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	1.6 (3.0)	0.56
3.0	3.0	1.9	1.7 (4.1)		
4.0	4.0	2.1	1.8 (4.8)		
5.0	5.0	2.0	1.9 (6.3)		

^a k_{obs1}, k_{obs2} and k_{obs3} for EDTA, bpy and Mn^{II}, respectively.

^b[bpy] = 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ and relative k_{obs2} are given in parentheses.

Rate dependence on complexing agents : In order to see the role of complexing agents, a series of kinetic runs were performed in presence of EDTA, bpy and Mn^{II} under similar experimental conditions of [Cr^{VI}], [D-glucose], [HClO₄] and temperature with those employed in the absence of these complexing agents. It was observed that the addition of a small quantity of EDTA or bpy gives a pronounced rate enhancement (Table 2). On the other hand, Mn^{II} shows no effect (Table 2). The catalytic effects of EDTA and bpy clearly reflect the involvement of these complexing agents somewhere before the rate-

determining step. The experiment clearly conforms that EDTA and/or bpy must be present in the inner coordination sphere of a chromium ion with a valency higher than three. Manganese(II) plays an important role (catalysis or inhibition or no effect) in the oxidation of organic reductants by Cr^{VI} 16,17. Under our experimental conditions ([Mn^{II}] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ to 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹), addition of Mn had no effect on the reaction rate (Table 2). This suggests that free Cr^{IV} species is not formed as an intermediate in this redox process.

Mechanism :

It is well known that in acid solutions, Cr^{VI} participates in acid-base equilibria and various species like Cr₂O₇²⁻, HCrO₄⁻, CrO₄²⁻, H₂CrO₄ and HCrO₃⁺ exist in aqueous solution¹⁸. The nature of these species depends on the pH of the medium and the concentration of potassium dichromate. Increase in rate constant with the increase in [HClO₄] indicates that the presence of H₂CrO₄ as a reactive species of Cr^{VI}. On the other hand, EDTA is a powerful complexing agent in aqueous solution as it exists in many forms under the conditions employed in our study (eq. (2)). bpy is a weak base and is also protonated as shown in eq. (3). The protonated species of bpy is a reactive and major existing species in presence of HClO₄ and it may undergo complexation with the reactive species of Cr^{VI}.

Taking into consideration all the above mentioned aspects, the following mechanisms (Schemes 1 and 2) are assumed to describe in a simplified form the effects of EDTA and bpy on the oxidation of D-glucose, respectively.

(1) In presence of EDTA (Scheme 1) :

Scheme 1

(2) In presence of bpy (Scheme 2) :

Scheme 2

In Schemes 1 and 2, eqs. (4) and (10) represent the formation of complexes (C1 and C3) with Cr^{VI} and the reactive species of EDTA and bpy, respectively. In the next step, complex C1/C3 reacts with a molecule of D-glucose to form termolecular chromate-ester like intermediate (C2/C4). In analogy with our previous results^{10,17}, we assume that these complexes undergo oxidative decomposition by a one step, two-electron oxidation-reduction mechanism leading to the formation of Cr^{IV} -EDTA/bpy complexes and lactone as the oxidation product of D-glucose. The Cr^{IV} -EDTA/bpy complex reacts with D-glucose to yield free radical and Cr^{III} complex. In the last step, the Cr^{V} complexes react with D-glucose (eqs. (9) and (15)).

A rate law consistent with Scheme 1 may be expressed as eq. (16) conforming to the observed first-order behaviour with respect to [D-glucose] at constant $[\text{H}^+]$.

$$v = -d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_{\text{T}}/dt = \frac{k_1 K_{es1} K_{a1} K_{c1} [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4^-] [\text{D-glucose}] [\text{EDTA}]_{\text{T}}}{(1 + K_{a1} [\text{H}^+])} \quad (16)$$

and the first-order rate constant,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 K_{es1} K_{a1} K_{c1} [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{D-glucose}] [\text{EDTA}]_{\text{T}}}{(1 + K_{a1} [\text{H}^+])} \quad (17)$$

Eq. (17) clearly explains the complex order dependence of the reaction on $[\text{H}^+]$ at constant [D-glucose] (Fig. 2). According to eq. (17), a plot of k_{obs} versus [D-glucose] should be linear passing through the origin with positive slope. Such plot has been realized in the present study.

Conclusion :

In the present study, the catalytic effect of EDTA and bpy on the oxidation of D-glucose by Cr^{VI} was examined.

Catalysis of Cr^{VI} oxidation of D-glucose by EDTA and/or bpy could probably be explained due to the formation of complex between Cr^{VI} and EDTA/bpy, which leads to the formation of Cr^{III}-EDTA/bpy complexes. On the other hand, addition of EDTA to an authentic Cr^{III} sample produced no change in the λ_{\max} values of Cr^{III} for *ca.* 72 h. We are unaware of any precedence in the redox chemistry of Cr^{VI}-carbohydrate system in the presence of complexing agents. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first evidence showing the catalytic role of EDTA and bpy in the oxidation of D-glucose by Cr^{VI}.

Experimental

Materials : D-Glucose (reductant), K₂Cr₂O₇ (oxidant), disodium salt of diamminetetra acetic acid, 2,2'-bipyridyl, acetic acid, manganese(II) chloride and mercuric chloride (Merck, India) were used as supplied and their stock solutions were prepared in double distilled (first time from alkaline KMnO₄), deionized and CO₂ free water. K₂Cr₂O₇ was finely ground and dried for 2 h at 383 K. EDTA solution was stored in a polyethylene bottle. To maintain the hydrogen ion concentration constant, HClO₄ (Fischer, 70% reagent grade) was used. 2,2'-Bipyridyl was first dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid and then diluted to the desired concentration. D-Glucose solution was kept in a refrigerator.

Kinetic measurements : All the reactions were started in glass-stoppered two-necked flask fitted with double walled condenser to check evaporation. The reaction was initiated by the addition of the thermally equilibrated D-glucose to a mixture containing Cr^{VI}, perchloric acid and other reagents pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was followed spectrophotometrically by measuring decay in the absorbance of Cr^{VI} at 360 nm on a Spectronic 21-D spectrophotometer. The pseudo first-order rate constants, k_{obs} , were obtained from the plots of log (absorbance) versus time. The reactions were carried out under pseudo first-order conditions using an excess of D-glucose over Cr^{VI}.

Evidence for free radical formation : In a typical experiment, Cr (= 5.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹) was added to a reaction mixture containing D-glucose (= 5.0×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹), HClO₄ (= 0.23 mol L⁻¹) and saturated HgCl₂

solution (10 cm³) in 50 cm³ volume. The mixture was heated to 323 K for five minutes. A white precipitate of Hg₂Cl₂ appeared as the reaction proceeded¹⁹, indicating the formation of free radicals during the reaction. Similar experiments conducted in presence of EDTA (= 5.0×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹) produced the same white precipitate. Controlled experiments (with D-glucose or Cr^{VI} only) did not show any precipitate formation.

References

1. A. Kumar and R. N. Mehrotra, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1975, **40**, 1248.
2. K. K. Sen Gupta, S. Sen Gupta and S. K. Mandal, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1986, **139**, 185.
3. S. Signorella, M. Rizotto, V. Daier, C. Frascaroli, D. Polopoli, D. Martino, A. Bousseksou and L. F. Sala, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1996, 1607.
4. Z. Khan, P. Kumar and Kabir-ud-Din, *Colloids and Surf. A: Physico Chem. Eng. Aspects*, 2004, **248**, 25.
5. P. Kumar and Z. Khan, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 2005, **340**, 1365.
6. M. K. Sugiyama, Tsuzuki and N. Haramaki, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1993, **305**, 261.
7. K. D. Sugden and K. E. Wetterhahn, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1996, **35**, 3727.
8. J. K. Beattie and G. P. Haight (Jr.), *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **17**, 93.
9. M. Mitewa and P. R. Bontchev, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1985, **61**, 241.
10. Z. Khan and Kabir-ud-Din, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2002, **27**, 832.
11. F. Hasan and J. Rocek, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 3181; 1973, **95**, 5421.
12. Z. Khan and Kabir-ud-Din, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 481.
13. J. F. Perez-Benito and C. Arias, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1993, **71**, 649.
14. R. N. F. Thomeley, A. G. Sykes and P. Gans, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1971, 1494.
15. K. K. Sen Gupta, S. Sen Gupta and S. N. Basu, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1979, **71**, 75.
16. M. A. Olatunji and G. A. Ayoko, *Polyhedron*, 1998, **7**, 11.
17. J. F. Perez-Benito, C. Arias and D. Lamhari, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 472.
18. T. Shen-Yang and Li Ke-an, *Talanta*, 1986, **33**, 775.
19. M. Krumpoic and J. Rocek, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 3206.